

ESiWACE Scheduler development and support activities

Deliverable D3.10

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This document describes the work done in the context of the ESIWACE project on the topic *Earth System Modelling scheduling* (Task3.3) whose ultimate goal is to build a supported, user-driven community around the Cylc meta-scheduler for complex climate and weather suites on HPC systems and support advanced analysis experiments in the areas of data analytics and multi-site, multi-model experiments. This deliverable provides an update on this topic with respect to the Deliverable D3.9 - ESIWACE Scheduler development and support activities.

The main focus of this effort relates to three aspects: Cylc developments (Task 3.3.2), Cylc Support Services (Task 3.3.3), and Scheduling Systems Development (Task 3.3.4).

In particular, (i) the Cylc developments have followed the priorities agreed at a workshop on workflows organised by the IS-ENES2 project (Lisbon, September 2016) and include optimisations which supports the aims of large ensembles on Exascale platforms as anticipated in the long term, arising from workflow management and production-ready versions of the ESIWACE demonstrators, (ii) the Cylc support has addressed needs from the community regarding Cylc deployment and configuration at major data centres in the community, and, finally, (iii) the scheduling systems development has addressed major points on this topic, like architectural aspects and integrated scenarios, about large-scale analytics workflows for multi-model/multi-site data analysis. Here there are opportunities to build links to ESDM middleware from work-package 4. Finally, from a networking perspective, the 3rd Workshop on Workflows (funded by ESIWACE) has been organised over the last months and will be held in Brussels in September with 18 speakers presenting talks on several workflow topics, more than 40 registrants, 3 roundtable discussions and 1 training session.

2. Conclusion & Results

During the period associated to this task (September 2015 start of ESIWACE - February 2017 for D3.9 and until July 2018 for D3.10) there have been about 700 pull requests (changes) merged into the Cylc repository and 100 into the Ophidia repository and about 200 closed issues opened by the community to fix problems or request enhancements.

Key highlights are:

- Modernisation of the Cylc client-server interaction using a RESTful API approach;
- Interface improvements for configuring parameterised tasks for simpler workflow logic;
- System optimisation and improvement of job management;
- Improvement of the Cylc documentation (a new suite design guide was written);
- Migration of the suite user interface (Rose Bush) to Cylc completed;
- Cylc bug fixes, improvements to robustness and improved testing;
- Review of workflow solutions;
- Data Analytics workflow development based on Ophidia;

- Architectural design sketches and workflows developments regarding multi-model analysis both in centralised and distributed scenarios;
- User engagement, prototyping and planning of Cylc support for EC-Earth;
- Organisation of the second ESIWACE workflow workshop in September 2018.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Introduction

This report covers the activities undertaken so far by the Met Office, CMCC, BSC and MPI-M under task 3.3 of WP3 Usability, which includes tasks 3.3.1 - 3.3.4.

MetO has provided all the ESIWACE resources to this deliverable but details are also provided on the effort provided from non-ESIWACE partners in the development of Cylc [1] and in Cylc related outreach to the wider community showing the benefit of the open and collaborative nature of the Cylc software development. The team acknowledges the critical importance of the input and leadership provided by Hilary Oliver (NIWA) in the development of Cylc.

Task 3.3.1: Scoping the work

An initial ESIWACE Cylc development and support plan was published in February 2016 (Milestone 1) [14]:

This was presented to the community at the joint IS-ENES ESIWACE workflow workshop held in Lisbon in September 2016:

<https://is.enes.org/events/final-is-enes2-workshop-on-workflow-solutions-1>

See in particular the presentation on this topic [15]. The workshop attendees agreed to the plan without any changes.

Task 3.3.2: Cylc development

Between 09 February 2017 (the date the previous report was written) and 10 July 2018 (the date this report was written):

- There were **21 code authors**, of which 9 were from Met Office. The main contributors with at least 10 pull requests (a pull request is a single, logical change to the codebase) to Cylc were:
 - Dr Hilary Oliver, NIWA (Cylc's original author)
 - Matt Shin, Met Office
 - Oliver Sanders, Met Office
 - Sadie Bartholomew, Met Office (joined team Oct 2017)
 - Declan Valters, Met Office (joined team Apr 2017, left team Oct 2017)
- In total, there were **348 pull requests** merged into the master and/or other supported branches, of which 229 were from the core team at Met Office. All pull requests were reviewed by at least a member of the Met Office's core team, and all but the most trivial pull requests were signed off by another member in the core team. Each pull request is a self contained change to the code base and they vary from simple one-liners through to large changes which may have taken months to code and test.
- There were **168 closed issues**, many of which were created by or on behalf of Cylc users to fix problems or request enhancements.

Details of the key changes in each Cylc release are available from the change log: <https://github.com/cylc/cylc/blob/master/CHANGES.md>

Key highlights for this reporting period:

- The team continued to capitalise on the migration of the **client-server interaction** to use a REST API via HTTPS. The API was simplified and modernised, with improved potential for future expansion. Service files were relocated and grouped together to reduce cluttering up the user space, removing items that would be irrelevant to their actual work from normal view. There were various improvements to allow Cylc to run smoothly on sites with restricted networks to meet local security needs. The number of client-server interactions were reduced to cut down network traffic and the load on suite servers. In particular, the interactions between GUIs and the suite server programs were consolidated and became more intelligent to reduce much unnecessary traffic which was impacting the scalability of the solution.
- There were continued efforts to improve the interface for configuring **parameterised tasks**. For example, integer parameters can now be defined using one or more range-and-step notation, and can be negative or positive. String parameters can now be used as full task names. There was also improved support to use parameters in templates for task names and environment variables in a task job. The introduction of these syntaxes in the suite configuration file allowed users to write cleaner workflow logic in fewer statements.
- There were various activities to **optimise the system**. For example, validation and start up time could be up to 6 times faster for some suites with complex interdependencies and cycling requirements. The main loop of the suite server program was modified to improve the management of sub-processes, and to intelligently adjust the sleep time to the level of activity. There was good progress in reducing memory usage by suite server programs by refactoring the code base with cleaner logic.
- There were various improvements to **job management**. The system now presents leaner job scripts to users with better start up logic making suites easier to read. The main logic for running a job was moved to a static script. Job error handling was improved, and the ability to have custom abort messages was added. Messaging logic was improved to allow jobs to send multiple messages in a single API call. This both reduces network traffic and ensures that messages are correctly identifiable between the task jobs and the suite server programs.
- A lot of effort went to the improvement of the documentation. In particular, a **new suite design guide** was written. Rose documentation was re-written and modernised, with a **new tutorial dedicated for Cylc suite development**. Relevant parts of the new Rose material would likely be moved to Cylc in due course. The new material was designed to be used for self-learning online, as well as in a taught training course environment. The aim here is to improve the quality of the suites that users develop which further encourages the sharing of suites and best practice.
- The work to migrate **Rose Bush** (the user interface for viewing suites and their status) to Cylc was completed providing access to the tool for sites using Cylc but not Rose. The change was under review at the time this report was being written.

It should be noted that the development effort described here covers the entire Met Office contribution to Cylc development which is considerably more than is funded by ESiWACE. The funding provided by ESiWACE enables the Met Office to maintain a much greater pace of development than would otherwise be possible. It also means we can prioritise the developments which are of most benefit to the Cylc community as a whole rather than focussing solely on Met Office priorities.

The team at Met Office attended PyCon UK 2017 and gave a talk on Cylc. The presentation can be watched on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wUD6VayhAz0>

During Dr Hilary Oliver's visit to the Met Office in June 2018, the core team held a number of meetings on current priorities and future directions of Cylc. In particular:

- The team proposed a new client-server architecture, which would allow Cylc to migrate from old native GUI technology to modern web technology that would be easier to develop and maintain, support the migration to Python 3, and improve future user experience.
- The team agreed on Python 3 migration strategy, which would happen after the implementation of the new client-server architecture. Python 2 will no longer be supported after 2020 and will start to be dropped from standard Linux distributions in advance of this date, so in the longer term this will be a barrier to adoption.
- In light of ever more complex suites seen in the user community, the team also discussed many other topics to improve Cylc, including:
 - Programmable API to define workflow and runtime.
 - Modular workflow and sub-graph management.
 - Repeating workflow in scopes beyond global cycling and parameters.
 - The relationship between a workflow task and a compute cluster job.
 - (All of these should allow Cylc to become a better tool for users to develop more complex workflow in increasingly challenging compute environments.)

Task 3.3.3: Support services

The demand for Cylc support is generally rather low, and are mainly installation issues on sites with restricted network setup. This can be seen as encouraging since it implies that sites that adopt Cylc do not, typically, need a large amount of support which validates both the system design and the quality of the supporting documentation. The low level of support needed has also meant that issues or questions which have been raised via Github, the Cylc Google group or via email have all been responded to promptly. In particular, the team maintains a vibrant discussion channel via the Cylc Google Groups. Further, the effort has been invested into product improvements that are driven by requests in the active user community and will hence make Cylc more attractive.

Demand for support services could increase dramatically if any new sites decide to start evaluating Cylc and ask for help with installation, training, etc. The ESiWACE funding means that this support is available

if required. However, if demand for the support services remains low this allows us to continue focussing on the development activities which are of clear benefit to the whole Cylc community.

Task 3.3.4 Scheduling Systems Development

This task, building on the Ophidia system, has focused around a set of activities - characterised by large volume of data, data distribution, multidimensionality and inherent data complexity - in the areas of **data analytics** and **multi-site, multi-model** experiments.

In particular, during the reporting period, the following activities were performed:

- **Review of workflow solutions:** to address data analytics and multi-site, multi-model analysis experiments from a workflow management perspective, a state of the art analysis of the available solutions have been performed. In particular the workflow management systems (WfMSs) reviewed in the context of the project have been classified as follows: *general purpose* (or *domain-agnostic*) and *specialised* solutions exploited to address climate & weather workflow needs.
- In the first category, major tools like Kepler [2,3] and Taverna [4] have been analysed in detail from a functional (provided features) and non-functional (performance, robustness, transparency) points of view. In summary, general purpose tools (i) often combine distributed web services and local applications into complex analysis pipelines, making them suitable for distributed scenarios, (ii) offer easy-to-use graphical interfaces to setup and monitor the experiments, which help with user adoption, (iii) do not provide specialised/domain-specific support (like for climate and weather applications), but rather a general approach/framework to build on top of it any kind of specific functionalities.

Tools like Cylc fall in the second category and, as documented in the previous tasks, provide a stronger support to climate and weather applications. In such category, but with a stronger emphasis on data analysis, it is also included the Ophidia framework [5,6,7], which provides big data analytics workflow capabilities.

- **Data analytics workflow development:** during the period, several activities have been performed regarding the improvement of the Ophidia workflow management capabilities to address end users' requirements for applications such as climate indicators. The workflow engine has been enhanced to improve processing chains and workflow interfaces (see Fig. 1) including loops (both iterative and parallel), conditional constructs, interactive support and cross-workflows synchronisation.

In particular, during the period, **82** commits have been performed on the Ophidia server module (<https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-server>, which is responsible for the workflow engine aspects), **6** issues have been closed and **10** pull requests have been merged. Some key technical aspects that have been addressed are:

- o Extensions of the JSON Response schema to include execution time information and control-info using a piggy-backing approach;
- o token management check for long-running workflows;

- new filters for HTC-based operators (parameter sweep jobs) negation support in filter for massive operations;
- expressions evaluation support in the OPH_SET operator;
- Support for comments in the JSON Request;
- Workflow checker improvement;
- Bug fixing activities.

NAME	DESCRIPTION
OPH_ELSE	Start the last sub-block of a selection block "if".
OPH_ELSEIF	Start a new sub-block of a selection block "if".
OPH_ENDFOR	Close a loop "for".
OPH_ENDIF	Close a selection block "if".
OPH_FOR	Implement a loop "for".
OPH_IF	Open a "if" selection block.
OPH_INPUT	It sends commands or data to an interactive task.
OPH_SET	Set a parameter in the workflow environment.
OPH_WAIT	Wait until an event occurs.

Fig. 1. Ophidia workflow interfaces.

- **Pure analytics workflows applications:** during the period, several activities have been performed with regard to the implementation of climate indicators as *pure* analytics workflows (DAGs consisting of Ophidia operators only). In this case, the JSON documents compliant with the Ophidia JSON Schema [8] have been developed to address climate scientists' needs regarding climate indicators. Some examples relate to the single-model Precipitation Trend Analysis (PTA) [9] and the Daily Temperature Range (DTR) [10].
- **Data-centre workflows applications with modelling, analytics and processing components:**
 - **Adoption of Cylc for operational chains by CMCC**
 With regard to this activity, some use cases running at data-centre level have been discussed with end-users at CMCC and implemented. In particular, during the period, a use case related to the fire danger prevention operational chain running at the CMCC Supercomputing Centre has been implemented. From an architectural standpoint, the proposed solution exploits a two-level workflow strategy based on Cylc and Ophidia, which entirely replaces the legacy (script-based) operational chain.
 In particular, with regard to the implementation carried out at CMCC:
 1. Cylc has been exploited to orchestrate, at the data centre level, the whole experiment in terms of data movement, data publication as well as analytics

workflow submission (as a “single” coarse-grain task). Cylc has been deployed on a dedicated VM and properly configured according to the Supercomputing Centre security policy settings.

2. Ophidia has been exploited to orchestrate the analytics workflow (as a DAG of fine-grain analytics tasks). Such workflow includes tens of operators that perform data processing, analysis, and visualization (e.g. maps production). To this end, Ophidia has been deployed on a dedicated analytics cluster with 100 cores in total, 5 fat nodes (256GB RAM/node), high-speed network connection, and 50TB storage using GFS cluster file-system.

Technical questions about Cylc set up at the CMCC Supercomputing Centre (CMCC SCC) and the two-level workflow strategy have been discussed and addressed with the UK Met Office Team through dedicated teleconferences. In future, beyond the activity planned for Task 3.3.4, CMCC plan to “port” the existing workflow implementation to the Athena HPC cluster running at the CMCC SCC, where integration with a scheduler (LSF, the Athena scheduler) will be also considered. Such activity will exploit the ESDM middleware from the Exploitability Work Package (WP4), which has been recently ported on the Athena cluster.

- **Adoption of Cylc for EC-Earth by BSC (planning, prototyping and approaches)**

Under the framework of this task, BSC started a demonstrator to run a simple EC-Earth use-case using the Cylc workflow engine and Rose suite specification. BSC started an e-mail interaction with the UK Met Office team asking for help with installation of Cylc, Rose and Rosie on a BSC virtual machine. BSC asked for advice on building a simple suite that runs dummy tasks on various systems including MareNostrum4. The installation was completed and the virtual machine is now running at BSC, although this approach is still not available system wide.

Having a working Cylc and Rose environment, a demonstrator suite, based on the 4871-cylc-runtime EC-Earth branch, was created. Revision [r5449](#) was checked in, where the suite configuration (runtime/cylc) folder was created. This supports running NEMO only (ece-nemo) and GCM (ece-ifs+nemo) configurations from a Cylc suite including simulation and post-processing tasks on MareNostrum4, using the Cylc BSC installation. The demonstrator suites are version controlled in an internal Subversion "Rosie" repository at BSC, but the possibility of setting up a Rosie repository hosted in the cloud is being considered. This would allow everyone in the EC-Earth community to access those suites and run at their site.

The planning at BSC, for the medium term Cylc and Rose adoption, comprises several fronts:

- Extend the EC-Earth demonstrator for enabling multi-member runs for seasonal/decadal climate prediction experiments and other use cases.
 - Create suites for the Air quality group using MONARCH air quality model.
 - Create suites for enabling automated tests, scalability and load balance analysis for EC-Earth.
 - Evaluate if Rosie can be adopted as a EC-Earth community tool for sharing and exchanging suite configurations.
 - Test the ECMWF Cylc installation instance with this EC-Earth demonstrator.
 - Further develop the EC-Earth Cylc runtime, to simplify the system by reducing the number of scripts involved and improve the way it can be modified and maintained.
 - Explore ways of including in Cylc / Rose several features implemented on Autosubmit [13], extensively used at BSC:
 - Capability to interact with git repositories through the experiment manager.
 - Wrappers to run clusters of jobs together (<http://autosubmit.readthedocs.io/en/latest/usage/wrappers.html>)
- **Multi-model analysis workflows:** During the period, two architectures have been defined for task management to implement a multi-model analysis experiment as a workflow. The following sub-sections describe two solutions that can work respectively with a *distributed* and a *centralized* approach. The Precipitation Trend Analysis, implemented as single-model indicator workflow (previously reported), has been considered as a test case and extended towards a multi-model analysis experiment. The reference context considered here for the multi-model analysis is the CMIP/ESGF.

- o **Multi-site (distributed solution)**

The proposed architectural solution (Fig. 2) implements a two-level workflow approach where the overall orchestration across sites is performed by a WfMS (e.g. Kepler) and the analytics one at the level of a single site is carried out by a local workflow engine (e.g. Cylc or Ophidia). In our test case Ophidia has been used both for the single-model part of the experiment and the final statistical analysis (two analytics workflows). The design was driven by the data distribution requirement inherently coming from the legacy ESGF infrastructure and the need avoid large-scale data movement by simply exploiting server-side analytics solutions. However, production environments can suffer from network instability, sites unavailability, services downtime, and non-uniform service release deployment across sites.

Fig. 2. Multi-site architecture for multi-model analysis workflows.

○ **Single site (centralized solution)**

In this case, the proposed architectural solution (Fig. 3) implements a one-level workflow approach where a data collection layer pre-staging and caching the data relevant for the analysis experiment has been added between the different sites hosting the output of the simulations and the WfMS. As such, a single analytics workflow can do the whole multi-model analysis experiment on a central location. In this case the design was driven by the limitations in a production environment mentioned in the previous section (multi-site distributed solution). A centralised storage location cannot represent a scalable solution for the whole CMIP data archive (approximately 20-30 PB foreseen for CMIP6), but can be a suitable approach if a single site can act as an analytics workflow-hub for one or a very small set of selected variables. As a consequence, multiple, distributed analytics-hubs could serve the entire community by addressing the full set of variables. Such scenario provides a new *variable-centric and analytics-hub-based* infrastructural paradigm, where workflow capabilities play a key role for **data analysis**, as opposed to the model-centric one currently implemented through the ESGF Data Nodes mostly serving **data access** needs. The proposed architectural approach has been implemented and tested through the multi-model version of the PTA test case (developed using Ophidia operators). The PTA multi-model workflow [11] has been executed and validated at the CMCC SCC on 11 models from CMIP5 experiment (for a total of 181 tasks). Figure 4 shows the runtime of the experiment. As an additional activity, the PTA workflow has been generalised to support the implementation of a variety of indicators in a multi-model fashion [12]. The solution

includes a multi-model framework, where single-model indicator workflows can be plugged as a black-box through a specific API.

Fig. 3. Single-site architecture for multi-model analysis workflows.

Fig. 4. A snapshot of single-site multi-model analysis workflow (runtime execution and output of the workflow experiment)

- **Organisation of the workflow workshop:** finally, during the period, the preparatory activity related to the organisation of a workshop on workflows has been performed. As a result, the workshop will be held in Brussels in September (13th-14th) and will also include training/hands-on sessions. At the time the report is being written, the registration has been closed with in excess of 40 registrants, 18 talks, 3 panel/round-table discussions, training on 2 workflow tools. The workshop information and agenda area available online at the following link: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/esiwace-workshop-on-workflows-1/esiwace-workshop-on-workflows>

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6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience has been supported through dissemination and networking actions put in place during the project. The most relevant ones are reported in the following:

- Cylc was presented to the community at the joint IS-ENES2 workshop on meta-data and workflow in Lisbon in September 2016:
<https://is.enes.org/events/final-is-enes2-workshop-on-workflow-solutions/jwsmg>

The plan was presented at the workshop:

<https://is.enes.org/events/final-is-enes2-workshop-on-workflow-solutions/slides/26Matthewsesiwace.pdf>

- Cylc was presented at PyCon UK 2017. The presentation can be watched on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wUD6VayhAz0>
- Scientific Data analytics using the Ophidia framework was presented at the ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers Como, Italy — May 16 - 19, 2016. See <https://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?doid=2903150.2911719>
- BSC presented plans for use of Cylc within EC-Earth to the EC Earth community meeting in Helsinki 29-31 May 2017.
- A paper is being prepared on techniques to improve the throughput of large-scale climate workflows by BSC and another one on distributed workflows for multi-model climate data analysis by CMCC.

Networking, training and dissemination activities will be the mean by which the uptake of the deliverables will be ensured. In this respect, the 3rd ENES Workshop on Workflows is an excellent example and opportunity to increase community awareness and to clarify the level of development and available support for the workflow tools presented in this deliverable. As a future plan, further efforts could address large conferences like the European Geosciences Union (with special regard the Earth & Space Science Informatics (ESSI) Division) where similar training/dissemination events could be proposed to a broad audience and the 14th IEEE eScience conference in Amsterdam.

Further, a community position paper about *multi-model analytics workflows scenarios, architectures and solutions* will be prepared by WP3 partners based on the activity carried out in this Work Package.

See also Section 9 on sustainability.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

One month delay.

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

In the DoA, the following was envisaged:

Task 3.3 ESM Scheduling [Lead: MetO. Participants: MPI-M, BSC, CMCC]

This task will maximise the chances of building a supported, user-driven community around the Cylc meta-scheduler for complex climate and weather suites on HPC systems.

Changes and/or difficulties for Task3.3 are reported below in more detail at the level of the following sub-tasks relevant for this deliverable: T3.3.2, T3.3.3, T3.3.4.

Task 3.3.2 Cylc Development [Lead: MetO; Participants: MPI-M] Development of service

Informed by the workshop and the governance activity, under the Lead of MetO and assisted by BSC and MPI-M, in cooperation with NIWA and inviting involvement from GFDL, Cylc will be developed to support a wider community and set of platforms. The development will consist of two activities: Firstly to refactor code to ensure continued supportability and to allow a wider community engagement in the code of Cylc; second, to develop any new features required by the community according to the results of the governance activity in particular considering the challenges of exploiting exascale computing in climate and weather applications in a pan-European context [D3.9].

Development effort has been enhanced as a result of less effort being required for support services due to investment in good on-line resources.

Task 3.3.3 Cylc Support Services [Lead: MetO; Participants: BSC] Provisioning of service

Informed by the workshop and the governance activity, training and support services will be provided to the community as prioritised by the governance activity. MetO will be responsible for level 2 support with level 1 support coming from local help-desk services. They will also be responsible for training, including the training of the local level 1 support.

The level of support needed has been less than envisaged at the planning stage as a result of good on-line support. The effort saved has been diverted to development of both the software and the on-line resources.

Task 3.3.4 Scheduling Systems Development [Lead: CMCC; Participant: BSC] Networking Activity, Joint research activity

The areas of data analytics and multi-site, multi-model experiments need special attention in terms of their scheduling. An initial workshop on these topics will develop ideas for system architectures and design sketches for the appropriate software solutions, and will show paths to first implementations. Where systems already exist like Autosubmit (supported by IS-ENES2 and adhering to PRACE guidelines), Ophidia, Cylc, and others, implementation strategies, possibly on the interaction between them, will be suggested informed by the governance.

The workshop has been moved to September 2018 (see activity reported in Task 3.3.4) as other workshops on this topic were organised over the last years as joint IS-ENES/ESiWACE events. Such strategy is helping to guarantee continuity in the series of workshops on this topic to the community (previous workshop in 2016 “Joint final IS-ENES2 workshop on Workflow Solutions in Earth System Modelling and Meta-Data Generation during Experiments” - supported by ESiWACE - <https://is.enes.org/events/final-is-enes2-workshop-on-workflow-solutions/jwsmg>).

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

The uptake of an “industrial strength” workflow manager such as Cylc needs both working level engagement and institutional level support. For any single activity, it is often quicker to improve existing (often script-based) workflow solutions. However, the benefits outweigh the overheads when implemented at the institutional level because of the economies of scale. The opportunities to realise these benefits are rare and are most likely to occur when there is a need for a significant step change in workflow complexity or a significant existing problem with workflow that needs to be overcome.

Cylc development and user interaction is performed by fully open forums that clarify that the development teams are (i) responsive to the user community in terms of features and bug fixes; (ii) committed to the scalability of the solution; (iii) planning to change Cylc to make it future proof; (iv) understand the importance of good documentation and quality assurance. These principles, alongside the existing level of adoption, provide the evidence required to make such a decision at an institutional level.

Despite an initial communication effort with internal users about a strategy change regarding the implementation of workflows at the data centre level, the migration to workflow tools like Cylc and Ophidia, especially for production-level operational chains, has valuable and recognised (both by end-users and developers) benefits and plus, with respect to bash script-based traditional approaches, in terms of fault tolerance, re-usability, productivity, and maintainability.

Long term sustainable development of workflows in EC-Earth is of key importance for the BSC Earth science department. BSC has been extensively using a workflow management system (WMS): Autosubmit, for running production-level workflows. A group of engineers in the Computational Earth Sciences team (CES) have been dedicated to the maintenance and implementation of the EC-Earth Autosubmit runtime environment and Autosubmit itself.

Recently a survey was run among the EC-Earth community to know about their use cases and asking about their needs and expectations from a workflow management system. Given that Cylc is gaining popularity among the climate and weather community, the BSC CES group, endorsed by the EC-Earth technical working group, agreed on (i) maintaining the Autosubmit option (ii) implement the Cylc / Rose option in the next 1-2 years. The goal in the medium term would be to adopt Cylc / Rose as the EC-Earth community tool to share and exchange workflows. The same CES resources that are dedicated to develop and maintain the Autosubmit runtime will be kept for developing the EC-Earth Cylc runtime. Part of the resources dedicated to Autosubmit package will be dedicated to the implementation of needed features for Cylc (see task 3.3.4).

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The data analytics workflows based on Ophidia (and the more articulated ones at data centre level based on Cylc) will take leverage on the new release of the ESDM middleware from the Exploitability Work Package (WP4) which has been recently ported on the Athena HPC system and the Ophidia dedicated cluster at the CMCC SCC. This activity is still ongoing and the final integration on a few representative test cases/workflows will be delivered by the end of 2018.

10. Full track of dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Location and dates	Audience	Zenodo record / link to website	Estimated number of persons reached
Presentation & Poster	CMCC Annual Meeting	June 5-6, 2018, Ugento (LE), Italy	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	http://www.cmcc.it/events/cmcc-annual-meeting-2018	130
Presentation	EC-Earth meeting	29-31 May 2017 at FMI in Helsinki	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)		60
Social Media	YuoTube video from PyCon conference	web	General public but aimed at Python community	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wUD6VayhAz0	250 views
Social Media	YouTube video for EC-Earth community	web	General public but aimed at EC-Earth community, to introduce Workflow Management Systems for EC-Earth	https://youtu.be/nyOR0G93Zvl	60 views
Presentation	PyCon UK conference	15-19 September 2017 Cardiff	Other: Python developer community	https://2017.pyconuk.org/	50

Peer reviewed articles

Type of scientific publication	Title of the scientific publication	DOI	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number, date	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Relevant pages	Public & private participation	Peer review	Is/Will open access provided to this publication
Publication in conference proceeding /workshop	An in-memory based framework for scientific data analytics	https://doi.org/10.1145/2903150.2911719	D. Elia, S. Fiore, A. D'Anca, C. Palazzo, I. Foster, D. N. Williams, G. Aloisio	ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers	May 16 - 19, 2016	ACM	New York, NY, USA	2016	6	NO	YES	NO
Article in Journal	Cylc: A Workflow Engine for Cycling Systems	https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00737	Hilary J Oliver, Matthew Shin, and Oliver Sanders	Journal of Open Source Software	July 23 2018	Journal of Open Source Software		2018	1	NO	YES	YES

Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <u>open access</u> be provided to this publication?
In preparation	Cloud-based multi-model analytics experiments on large-scale, distributed climate change datasets.	S. Fiore, M. Plóciennik, C. M. Doutriaux, C. Palazzo, J. Boutte, T. Zok, D. Elia, M. Owsiak, A. D'Anca, Z. Shaheen, R. Bruno, M. Fargetta, M. Caballer, G. Moltó, I. Blanquer, R. Barbera, M. David, G. Donvito, D. N. Williams, V. Anantharaj, D. Salomoni, G. Aloisio	IEEE Access (http://ieeaccess.ieee.org/)	Yes
In preparation	Techniques to improve the throughput of large-scale climate workflows	D. Manubens Gil, L. Batista Leite, M. Castrillo, J. López de la Franca, O. Mula Valls, K. Serradell	-	-

Proposed	Multi-model analytics workflows scenarios, architectures and solutions	To be defined	To be defined	Yes.
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Not Applicable